

RECYCLING POST-CONSUMER FIBRES FROM WOOD WASTE INTO NEW FIBRE- BOARDS

MDF

HDF

Medium- and high-density fibreboards (MDF, HDF) are wood-based panels (WBP), manufactured by combining wood fibres with an adhesive and compressing the mixture under heat. By adjusting the adhesive formulation, pressing conditions and the use of additives, boards can be made with different properties, including moisture resistance, fire retardancy and load-bearing capacity.

APPLICATIONS

MDF and HDF are widely used in furniture manufacturing, interior design, and the construction sector, offering functional and decorative uses in kitchens, offices, bedrooms, and living rooms. When painted, lacquered, or laminated, they provide a broad range of aesthetic options.

Their structure is well-suited to industrial processing techniques such as drilling, cutting, milling, incl. 3D surfaces, enabling applications for wall cladding, partitions, kitchen cabinetry, shelving, upholstered furniture components, packaging, and laminate flooring.

ACHIEVEMENTS

EcoReFibre project demonstration shows that MDF and HDF with recycled fibres achieve performance comparable to reference panels, confirming technical feasibility.

INCORPORATING RECYCLED POST-CONSUMER MDF FIBRES INTO NEW FIBREBOARDS

At lab scale, the incorporation of 15% and 25% of fibres obtained from post-consumer fibreboards into new panels was successfully demonstrated. Two extraction technologies provided the fibres: “modified thermal mechanical pulping (mTMP)” developed by the Dresden Institute for Wood Technology (IHD) and the so called “wet process” by Dieffenbacher. These fibres were then used to produce panels in a conventional lab press. The resulting physical and mechanical properties aligned with reference panels in most aspects (e.g. bending strength, thickness swelling, stiffness). However, internal bond, panel density and surface quality required some optimisation. Overall, incorporating 15% recycled fibres yielded better performance than 25%.

Following the lab results, industrial trials were conducted. A trial using fibres produced by Dieffenbacher’s wet process replaced virgin fibres at 5%, 10% and 15% in HDF production. They had to be blended unglued with the virgin fibres that were slightly overglued to achieve a standard overall gluing ratio. The trial confirmed that up to 15% recycled fibres can be incorporated into thin HDF without reducing or affecting line productivity, surface quality and paintability. Swelling and modulus of elasticity showed no significant changes, while both bending strength and internal bond decreased. Due to the absence of adhesive on the post-consumer fibres, the latter results were expected and could not be balanced with a 10% glue increase. Workability tests found little or no change in permeability; cutting and milling quality remained good and no critical issues from the recycled fibres were found.

In addition to post-consumer fibreboards, two more trials were carried out using post-consumer solid wood as input: one for MDF and one for thin HDF. The solid wood was processed in a conventional thermo-mechanical pulping process to obtain fibres. For both, results showed that if the material is well sorted and cleaned, it can be integrated into production. Post-consumer solid wood was crushed and blended with virgin wood chips. Panels containing up to 25% recycled fibres met all physical, mechanical and internal requirements (EN 622-5), with properties comparable to reference boards, and without reducing line productivity or degrading mechanical and swelling properties.

In the MDF trial, all samples surfaced with melamine resin-impregnated decorative paper showed no visual defects or processing issues, confirming suitability for decorative paper surfacing. Migration of harmful substances testing proved all quantified elements were below EN 71-3 thresholds, confirming toy safety compliance and no performance impact from recycled wood incorporation.

In thin HDF, a slight improvement in some properties was even observed. However, as these boards are produced in a single layer and are particularly sensitive to impurities, any loss of material quality can affect the final product, also risking damage to the press. Visual inspection occasionally revealed surface imperfections from tiny plastic fragments, including removable pieces that left microholes and local uplifted areas. These defects can affect subsequent finishing such as painting or foiling.

FUTURE CHALLENGES

Complete feedstock purity was identified as the main challenge for increasing recycled content. Even the 95% purity level reached was not enough, indicating the need for perfectly sorted and cleaned material. In addition, optimised logistics and expanded collection networks are needed to ensure a stable supply of high-quality material.

At plant level, adaptations are required to integrate recovered wood into existing production lines while maintaining compliance with quality and performance standards. These concern sifter capacity, sorting, cleaning and blending.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based, carbon storing material, wood is a key driver for Europe's circular bioeconomy. Reintegrating post-consumer WBPs into production helps close material loops and extend the lifespan of wood. Through horizontal recycling of WBPs, the material value is maintained and the dependence on virgin wood is reduced.

An innovative waste sorting line and smart recycling technologies enable end-of-life WBPs to be broken down into fibres and particles which are then reintegrated into new panel production. Industrial trials have shown that MDF/HDF can incorporate up to 25% recycled wood while achieving performance similar to reference panels. From an economic perspective, increasing recycling can help broaden the raw material base and support stabilising volatile virgin wood prices. Of course, also investments in recycling equipment and process adaption are required for industrial-scale production.

By fostering a circular value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the EcoReFibre project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), while aligning with the upcoming Circular Economy Act (CEA).

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSES THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

CONTACT

SONAE ARAUCO

Portugal | Spain | Germany | South Africa

Adelaide Alves
Group R&D Director

aalves@sonaearauco.com

HOMANIT

Germany | Poland | Lithuania

Matthias Schulte
Head of Technology

m.schulte@homanit.de

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos
Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

PARTNERS

 EcoReFibre

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**Funded by
the European Union**